

PRINCIPLES OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Azimova Mahfuza Abdusamatovna

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

Teacher of Department of Foreign Languages and Literature.

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Abstract.

This article provides the principles and strategies that needed to facilitate the management of classroom.

Keywords: principles, strategies, instructors, knowledge, students, classroom management

INTRODUCTION

Most teachers enter the teaching profession because they believe they can make a positive impact on the lives of children and young people. Although teachers have the power to change students' lives, the process can be complicated, especially when dealing with behavior. Student problem behavior, along with school discipline, is consistently cited as one of the top concerns for teachers¹, one of the biggest demands on time, and in some cases, leading to their decision to leave education. When teachers fail to manage their classrooms effectively, students perform poorly. Therefore, it is essential to create a positive and productive learning environment for overall success to support all teachers and students in getting the most out of their learning experience. The purpose of this guide is to introduce evidence-based classroom practices for classroom management, such as those associated with positive behavior change and supports (PBIS), as an approach to creating an effective classroom management system.

WHAT IS CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT?

Classroom management is defined as a teacher's method for maintaining order in the classroom that is conducive to student achievement. This method typically consists of evidence-based strategies that are implemented during classroom-wide, small group, and intensified when instructing individual students. However, implementing strategies independent of an established structure such a management system or framework can be less impactful and less efficient in achieving a teacher's desired outcome. The effectiveness of classroom strategies is maximised when:

- *strategies are implemented within a school-wide multi-tiered behavioural framework, such as PBIS*
- *classroom and school-wide expectations and systems are directly linked*
- *classroom strategies are merged with effective instructional design, curriculum, and delivery*

¹ Gable, R. A., Tonelson, S. W., Sheth, M., Wilson, C., & Park, K. L. (2012). Importance, usage, and preparedness to implement evidence-based practices for students with emotional disabilities: A comparison of knowledge and skills of special education and general education teachers. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 35(4), 499-519. <https://doi.org/10.1353/etc.2012.0030>

- *classroom-based data are used to guide decision-making².*

Classroom management consists of techniques and attitudes, through which the instructors exercise control on the classroom environment, so the learning of the students get up-graded. In accordance to the research studies, in some cases, the students do get involved in conflicts and disagreements with each other. Hence, when the classroom management will take place in an appropriate manner, the conduct and behaviour of the individuals will get redirected. Classroom management is action-oriented and goal-oriented (Johnston, 2020). When the educationists are conducting research on the management of the classroom, they need to take into consideration various factors, i.e. teaching-learning methods, instructional strategies, teaching-learning materials, needs and requirements of the students, resources and infrastructure, academic goals and objectives, traits of morality, ethics, norms, values, principles and standards, development of motivation among students and up-grading the overall system of education. Therefore, when the instructors and students are informative in terms of these factors, the task of classroom management will take place in an efficacious manner. In the implementation of the task of classroom management in an effectual manner, the instructors and the students will need to work in collaboration and integration with each other. It is not the sole job duty of the instructors, but they need to obtain support and assistance from their students as well. They assign job duties to the students, which they carryout in their presence as well as absence. For example, the students, belonging to all grade levels need to aware of the fact that they need to maintain cleanliness, and be well-aware in terms of ways of promoting discipline. When the instructors give any assignments, tasks or activities, they need to carry them out and ensure they get completed on time. In other words, depicting efficiency, possessing effective communication skills, time management skills and treating others with respect and courtesy are regarded as crucial factors that are needed in carrying out the task of classroom management in an efficient manner. The instructors impart knowledge to the students in terms of these factors in schools. Whereas, in higher educational institutions, they are usually aware of these factors.

How to build classroom management strategies

A. Fun classroom management strategies

- **There is never a “dead” time**

If you want the class to be orderly, never give students time to talk and work alone, which means the teacher must cover well. For example during literature class, when students are talking, the teacher can ask those students about the content of the old lesson. Asking questions related to the lesson students will brainstorm, and there will be no more time to talk

- **Get playful**

- **Intervene humbly**

Classroom Management Skills help teachers to avoid many stressful situations with students if they stay calm and solve problems gently, which is one of the most necessary factors of Classroom Management Skills.

² Office of Special Education Programs. (2015). *Supporting and responding to student behaviour: Evidence-based classroom strategies for teachers*. Washington DC: Office of Special Education Programs. Retrieved from www.pbis.org

A good teacher must try hard not to make one student the focus of attention. Teachers can walk around the classroom, anticipating what might happen before it happens. Treat undisciplined students naturally, without distracting other students.

For example, during the lecture, the teacher should use the “**recalling the name method**” If you see someone talking or doing something else, you should naturally mention their name in the lesson: “Alex, do you find this result interesting?”

Suddenly Alex hears his teacher calls his name. He definitely will return to seriousness without the whole class noticing.

Attention strategies in the classroom

Classroom Management Skills require teachers to bring surprising and fascinating lessons to students. It makes you hone your skills in building Classroom Response Systems by using supporting tools such as presentations, polls, games, and surveys.

• Start the school day with fun and delight

Students love to participate in classes with lovely teachers and engaging teaching methods³. Therefore, try to start your day with joy and raise the spirit of learning for your students, which will make students more interested in class.

• Do not start if you are unnoticed.

Before you start your lessons, you have to confirm that the students in the class pay attention to what you teach. Do not try to teach when students are noisy and inattentive. Inexperienced teachers sometimes think the classroom will be quiet once the lesson begins. Sometimes this works, but students may think you accept their disinterest and allow them to talk as you teach.

The attention method of Classroom Management Skills means you will wait and not start until everyone is still⁴. Teachers will stand still after the class has been silent for 3 to 5 seconds before speaking in a barely audible voice. (A teacher with a soft voice usually quiets the classroom more than a teacher who speaks loudly).

• Positive Discipline

Use rules that describe the good behavior you want your students to learn, not list things they should not do.

- “Please walk in the room gently” instead of “Do not run in the class”
- “Let’s solve the problems together” instead of “No fighting”
- “Please leave your gum at home” instead of “Do not chew gum”

Talk about the rules as things you want them to do. Let students know that these are what you expect them to keep in the classroom.

Do not hesitate to praise. When you see a person with good conduct, recognize it immediately. No words are needed; just a smile or a gesture can encourage them.

• Keep great faith in your students.

Always believe that students are obedient children. Reinforce that belief through the way you talk to your students. As you start a new school day, tell students what you want. For

³ Gage, N. A., Scott, T., Hirn, R., & MacSuga-Gage, A. S. (2018). The relationship between teachers’ implementation of classroom management practices and student behaviour in elementary school. *Behavior Disorders*, 43, 302–315.

⁴ Algozzine, B., Wang, C., & Violette, A. S. (2011). Re-examining the relationship between academic achievement and social behaviour. *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions*, 13, 3-16.

example, *"I believe you are good students and love to learn. You understand why you should follow the rules and should not lose focus in the lecture"*

- **Let the whole class compete with the teacher.**

"If the class is disorderly, the teacher will get points, and vice versa; if the class is great, the class will get points."

Sometimes it is possible to point out who is disorderly and deduct points for the whole team because of that person. Pressure from the class will make individuals will listen. It helps each individual not to make noise and to enhance the sense of responsibility not to let the class/team be affected by them⁵.

Building classroom management skills are challenging because it requires teachers to learn and change constantly. Especially no student is the same, so they need to apply various classroom management skills to different stages and objects.

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⁵ <https://ahaslides.com/blog/classroom-management-skills/>

